

Ionophoretic Amino Acid Studies on Metal-Ligand Interaction (Metal(M)(III)-Methionine System)

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Paper electrophoresis was applied to study metal complexes in solution. A significant development in the determination of stability constant of complexes was made by Jokl¹. The use of paper electrophoresis for the study of metal complexes with single ligand has been well established in our laboratory^{2,3}. The present work is an extension of this technique and reports our observations on binary complexes Fe^{III}/Cr^{III}-methionine system.

Results and Discussion

Metal(M)-methionine binary system : The plot of the overall mobility of a metal spot against pH gives a curve with a number of plateau (Fig. 1). The first one corresponds to a region in which metal ions are uncomplexed. The second plateau in each case with positive mobility, indicates formation of 1 : 1 complex of cationic nature. With increases in pH, the mobility decreases, giving rise to the third plateau in posi-

tive region, indicating an cationic nature of the metal complexes. The prominent ligating properties of unprotonated anionic species of methionine rule out any such property to Zwitterion⁴. Further increase in pH has no effect on the mobility of metal ions. The complexation of metal ions with the methionine anion [L⁻] may be represented as

where, M³⁺ is the trivalent Fe and Cr ions, [L⁻] the ligand (methionine), ML²⁺, ML₂⁺ are the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes, K₁, K₂ the first and second stability constants.

The spot moves under the influence of electric field, and its overall mobility (U) can be represented as

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L^{-}] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L^{-}]^2}{1 + K_1 [L^{-}] + K_1 K_2 [L^{-}]^2} \quad (3)$$

where, u₀, u₁ and u₂ are the mobilities of the uncomplexed, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes respectively. Stability constant of metal ions with methionine anion may be calculated with the help of equation (3). For calculating the first stability constant (K₁), the region between the first and second plateau is pertinent. The overall mobility (U) will be equal to the arithmetic mean of the mobilities of the uncomplexed metal ion (u₀) and that of the first complex (u₁) at a pH where, K₁ = 1/[L⁻]. With the help of the dissociation

Fig. 1. Mobility curves for the metal-methionine systems : (Δ) Fe^{III}-methionine and (O) Cr^{III}-methionine.

tion constants of methionine ($k_1 = 10^{2.25}$, $k_2 = 10^{9.00}$), $[L^-]$ is determined for the pH by using equation (4), from which K_1 can be calculated

$$[L^-] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + \frac{[H]}{k_2} + \frac{[H]^2}{k_1 k_2}} \quad (4)$$

where, $[L_T]$ is the total concentration of methionine and k_1 and k_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of methionine. K_2 can be calculated by taking into consideration the region between second and third plateau of the mobility curve.

The stability constants ($\log K$) of ML and ML_2 complexes of metal-methionine have been found to be (7.95, 12.65) and (7.52, 12.42) for the Fe^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes respectively, at $\mu = 0.1M$ and 35° .

The precision of the method is limited to that of paper electrophoresis. However, uncertainty in the result is $\pm 5\%$. Though it can not replace the most reliable methods, but it is a new approach worth developing.

It can be concluded that methionine may be used to reduce the levels of Fe^{3+} and Cr^{3+} from biological systems.

Experimental

The apparatus and procedure were the same as described earlier³. Solutions of iron(III) and chromium(III) perchlorate were prepared by first precipitating out the metal carbonates from 0.1 M solution of sulphates or nitrate of Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} with solution of sodium car-

bonate (AnalaR). The precipitate was washed with water and treated with calculated amount of perchloric acid.

Metal spots were detected on the paper using potassium ferrocyanide solution (B.D.H.) for Fe^{II} and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) (E. Merck) for Cr^{II} . A saturated aqueous solution (0.9 ml) of silver nitrate was diluted with acetone to 20 ml. Glucose, as the black spot, was detected by spraying with this solution and then with 2% ethanolic NaOH.

The background electrolytes used in the study of binary complexes were 0.1 M perchloric acid and 0.01 M methionine. Stock solutions of 9.0 M perchloric acid, 2.0 M sodium hydroxide and 0.5 M methionine were prepared from AnalaR grade chemicals (B.D.H.).

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